

Project Name	Robotic solution for monitoring rehabilitation process (ROSMON)
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Dissemination type	Report (whitepaper)
Dissemination level	Public
Date of publication	26 th February 2022

This Technology Demonstrator has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the DIH-HERO grant agreement no 825003.

Background

MetraLabs GmbH Neue Technologien und Systeme of Germany and Digiotouch OU of Estonia won a Technology Demonstrator (TD) cascade funding grant from the EU Horizon 2020 (H2020) DIH-HERO project. The major aim of the TD open call was to stimulate cross-border collaboration among European SMEs which are working in the area of Healthcare Robotics. The awarded project is called ROSMON.

The goal of ROSMON is to demonstrate and commercialize an innovative robotic solution for monitoring patients’ rehabilitation process after total knee/hip arthroplasty by automatically collecting data on the patients’ recovery process during in-patient, outpatient treatments, and at home. The proposed system makes use of a novel prototype of a mobile therapy robot collecting data on the patients’ gait training during in- and outpatient physiotherapy as well as smartwatches for gathering activity data, particularly during times outside of therapy sessions.

The problem

From the perspective of a physician or therapist, patients requiring rehabilitation are kind of “black box”. Their real physical behavior is not known a priori. The underlying hypothesis was that it is important for patient treatment to have a better understanding of the physical activities of the patients for improving treatment schemes. In other words, there is a lack of precise information about the level of daily activity especially after discharge from a hospital and during rehabilitation. Furthermore, it depends on the individual patient's life situation how much additional self-training can be recommended after a finished rehab. Recovery after surgery can be disrupted by too much or too little movement. Therefore, personalising a rehabilitation process is not possible at rehabilitation clinics.

Summary of ROSMON solution

The mobile robot system of MetraLabs GmbH (ROSMON coordinator) is a prototype of the **world's first robot for mobile gait training**, collecting data on the patient during his/her hospital stay and

during outpatient rehabilitation. Activities during the project included tests of various camera systems, data collection with patients, and development of algorithms for evaluating a gait mode. The robotic system will be marketed by tediro GmbH, a spin-off of the ROSMON coordinator MetraLabs. Digiotech brings its IoT expertise by providing a seamless and secure connection of the data collected by the robot (which acts as an IoT sensor device) to its cloud-based Paradise platform. In addition to that, smartwatches are used to collect data on patients' physical activity which are also integrated to the Paradise platform. Utilization of smartwatches in combination with the cloud platform are novel services in the context of rehabilitation robotics and together they bridge an important gap for those phases where the patients are out of sight of the therapists/physicians, for instance when being at home during the recovery phase. The robot and smartwatch data for each patient allows physicians/therapists to personalize the rehabilitation process for each patient.

The technical solution

To address the above-mentioned healthcare challenges, the ROSMON partners co-designed a smartwatch and secure cloud computing powered mobile therapy solution. This novel and upgraded solution monitors patients' activity levels post-surgery which can positively influence the rehabilitation treatment schemes paving the way for personalising them and optimising the resource utilisation of hospitals and rehabilitation clinics.

In its implementation, MetraLabs developed algorithms to evaluate gait patterns of the patients during training with the robot. A smartwatch from Withings, which is an approved class I medical device in the European Union, was provided to patients. The activity data were integrated into Digiotech's cloud-based, secure Paradise platform in addition to securely integrating the mobile therapy robot data. Dashboards were developed to visualise the smartwatch data that help assessing the activity level of the patients.

Clinicians are provided with a secure access to the dashboard and use the information on patient activities to improve their rehabilitation treatment schemes. In combination with the findings from tracking the data during the stay in hospital, intermediate stays at home and then during inpatient and outpatient rehabilitation, individual rehabilitation recommendations can be tailored directly to the patient – using this system – in order to neither strain the healing process by overdosing nor inhibit it by underdosing (low activity level).

Clinical study and validation at the “Waldkliniken Eisenberg” hospital

The project included a clinical study and validation of the technical solution at the “Waldkliniken Eisenberg” hospital, one of the largest clinics in Germany for elective surgery of the lower limb. The aim of this trial was to evaluate the "three-point gait training" application and collect data on two point-gait for improving the algorithms. The trial involved 24 patients, of which five were equipped with the smartwatch and their data were securely transmitted to Digiotech's Paradise platform (it was deployed at a cloud server located in Frankfurt). After over 90% of the trainings, patients were satisfied

or very satisfied with the training. Ethics approval was obtained for the clinical study, validation, and such data transfer.

Assessment of the project outcomes

Several physiotherapists, mainly from inpatient rehabilitation clinics, were surveyed to discuss the results of the project. They confirmed that the solution could be easily integrated into existing work processes. There were mixed views on the utility of the activity data for further improving the healing processes. These views partially depend on the indication: patients who are affected by cardiovascular diseases would benefit more from the solution. The therapists also stressed that the system would help increase patient motivation. Finally, also reimbursement opportunities were confirmed.

The market

The novel rehabilitation monitoring system of ROSMON addresses a market potential of 6-7 million patients annually, with an anticipated market size of \$7.6 Billion by 2026, growing at a CAGR of ~19.8% through the years. It indicates increased maturity of adopting one-stop solution by healthcare institutions and by patients making ROSMON highly timely for the market.